

Syntheses and Biological Activity of 5-(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole and 4-[(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole and related Systems

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5-(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (2) and 1H-substituted-pyrazoles (3a-c) were synthesised and a few reactions of 2 were studied. 4-[(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (9) and its corresponding 1-acetyl (10) and 1-phenyl (11) derivatives have also been synthesised and all the compounds have been screened against a few microorganisms for antibacterial activity.

IN previous papers¹⁻⁵ we reported the syntheses and antibacterial screening of various heterocyclic compounds having pyrazole, pyrazoline and triazole moiety. We report herein the syntheses of 5-(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (2) and 4-[(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (9) and their derivatives along with screening of antibacterial activity.

The present communication deals with the synthesis of hitherto unreported 5-(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (2) in 85% yield by the reaction of 3-(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (1) with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. The ketone (1) was obtained in 95% yield by reacting 1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde with acetophenone in alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The ketone (1) was also reacted with phenyl hydrazine and other substituted-hydrazines in glacial acetic acid to yield substituted-1H-pyrazoles (3a-c) (Scheme 1). The

Scheme 1

reactions of the 1H-pyrazole (2) were further studied by subjecting it to arylation with benzoyl chloride and acylation with aliphatic acids using direct and indirect methods. The reactions of the 1H-pyrazole (2) with various sulphonyl chlorides afforded the corresponding sulphonamide derivatives (6a-d) and its nitrosation afforded the N-nitroso derivative (7) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Scheme 3 explains the synthesis of 4-[(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (9) and 4-[(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (11) by reacting 3-[(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-2,4-pentanedione (8) with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol and phenyl hydrazine in glacial acetic acid.

The ketone (8) was obtained by coupling acetylacetone with diazotised solution of 1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenamine. Acylation of the pyrazole (9) with glacial acetic acid afforded 1-acetyl-4-[(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (10).

zole (10) in 55% yield. Similarly, the ketone (8) when reacted with hydrazine hydrate using glacial acetic acid afforded only 45% of 10.

Scheme 3

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded with a Bruker Spectrospin (80 MHz) instrument, and the ir spectra (KBr) with a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. Tlc plates (Merck, silica gel G, 0.25 mm) were developed in hexane/ethanol/petroleum-ether (b.p. 60-80°) mixture (4 : 3 : 3) in all cases.

1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde : It was synthesised from acenaphthene, *N*-methylformanilide and phosphorous oxychloride in *o*-dichlorobenzene by the reported method⁶.

3-(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (1) : Freshly distilled acetophenone (5.16 g, 0.043 mol) was dissolved in aqueous alcoholic NaOH (1.1 g, 0.021 mol NaOH, 6 ml ethanol and 10 ml water). The mixture was cooled to 0° and 1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde (7.83 g, 0.043 mol) was added with stirring. When the addition was complete, the temperature was raised to ~25° with vigorous stirring until the product began to form (about 2 h), and then allowed to stand overnight. The separated product was filtered, washed with cold water (5 × 20 ml), until the washings were neutral and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (11.6 g, 95%), m.p. 113° (Found : C, 88.70 ; H, 5.62. C₂₁H₁₆O requires : C, 88.73 ; H, 5.63%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3000 (CH₂ alkene), 2910 (CH₂ of acenaphthene) and 1650 (C=O), 970 cm⁻¹ (C-H out-of-plane def., *trans*-disubstituted alkene, CH=CH).

5-(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (2) : The compound 1 (2.84 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (50 ml), 99%

hydrazine hydrate (1 ml, 0.015 mol) added and the mixture was refluxed gently for 2 h. The ethanol was then concentrated and allowed to cool. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ethanol (2 × 20 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol to give a pale brown solid (2.53 g, 85%), m.p. 133° (Found : C, 84.52 ; H, 6.03 ; N, 9.35. C₂₁H₁₈N₂ requires : C, 84.56 ; H, 6.04 ; N, 9.39%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3340 (NH), 2920 (CH₂ of acenaphthene), 1600 (C=N, pyrazoline) and 1380 cm⁻¹ (CH₂ of pyrazoline).

5-(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1,3-diphenyl-1H-pyrazole (3a) : 3-(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (0.426 g, 0.0015 mol) and an equimolar amount of phenylhydrazine were refluxed in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) for 3 h. The mixture was left at room temperature and the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water (2 × 20 ml), and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid (0.449 g, 80%), m.p. 212° (Found : C, 86.66 ; H, 5.87 ; N, 7.43. C₂₇H₂₂N₂ requires : C, 86.63 ; H, 5.88 ; N, 7.49%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2900 (CH₂ of acenaphthene), 1600 (C=N, pyrazoline) and 1390 cm⁻¹ (CH₂ of pyrazoline). A similar procedure was employed for the preparation of 3b and 3c except that 4-carboxylphenyl- and 4-nitrophenyl-hydrazines were used instead of phenyl hydrazine : 3b (0.439 g, 70%), m.p. 260° (glacial acetic acid) ; 3c (0.359 g, 57%), m.p. 245° (glacial acetic acid).

Aroylation of 2 with benzoyl chloride (4) : The compound 2 (0.447 g, 0.0015 mol) and benzoyl chloride (0.2 ml, 0.00175 mol) were dissolved in dry pyridine (10 ml) and stirred at room temperature for 1 h after which the reaction mixture was treated with cold dilute HCl (2 N). The resulting solid was filtered and washed successively with water, cold NaOH (2%) and water, and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, (0.545 g, 87%), m.p. 209° (Found : C, 83.52 ; H, 5.45 ; N, 6.92. C₂₈H₂₂N₂O requires : C, 83.58 ; H, 5.47 ; N, 6.96%).

1-Formyl-5-(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (5a). **Method A** : Compound 2 (0.298 g, 0.001 mol) was refluxed in formic acid (10 ml) for 2 h. The solution was then concentrated and a little ethanol added. On cooling, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with water (3 × 20 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol, (0.306 g, 94%), m.p. 174° (Found : C, 80.94 ; H, 5.53 ; N, 8.53. C₂₂H₁₈N₂O requires : C, 80.98 ; H, 5.52 ; N, 8.59%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2925 (CH₂ of acenaphthene), 1600 (C=O, N-C=O), 1620 (C=N, pyrazoline) and 1360 cm⁻¹ (CH₂ of pyrazoline). A similar procedure was followed for the preparation of 5b and 5c except that acetic acid and propionic acid were used instead of formic acid : 5b (0.306 g, 90%), m.p. 144° (ethanol) ; 5c (0.309 g, 84%), m.p. 155° (ethanol).

Method B : To compound 1 (0.426 g, 0.0015 mol) dissolved in formic acid (15 ml), 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.1 ml, 0.002 mol) was added and the mixture refluxed for 2 h. The solvent was then

removed under reduced pressure and the residual matter diluted with water. The product (5a) precipitated, was filtered, washed with water (2 × 20 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol, (0.391 g, 80%), m.p. 174°. Analytical and spectroscopic data were identical with the sample prepared by Method A. Instead of formic acid, acetic acid and propionic acid were used and a similar procedure was employed for the preparation of 5b and 5c. The yield of 5b and 5c by this method was 87% and 72% respectively which was observed to be less than the yield of 5a-c synthesised from the compound 2.

Condensation of 2 with 4-methyl phenyl sulphonyl chloride (6a): A solution of 2 (0.447 g, 0.0015 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was cooled in an ice-bath and 4-methyl phenyl sulphonyl chloride (0.333 g, 0.00175 mol) was added. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature and was then treated with cold dilute HCl (2 N). The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water (3 × 20 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol, (0.529 g, 78%), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 74.37; H, 5.29; N, 6.15; S, 7.04. $C_{28}H_{24}N_2O_2S$ requires: C, 74.34; H, 5.31; N, 6.19; S, 7.08%). A similar procedure was employed for the preparation of 6b and 6c except that 4-acetaminophenyl and 5-acenaphthene sulphonyl chlorides were used instead of 4-methyl phenyl sulphonyl chloride: 6b (0.446 g, 60%), m.p. 205° (ethanol); 6c (0.424 g, 55%), m.p. 185° (ethanol).

Hydrolysis of 6b in dilute HCl (1:1) yield the 1-[(4-aminophenyl)sulphonyl] derivative (6d) (0.442 g, 65%), m.p. 276° (ethanol) (Found: C, 71.56; H, 5.07; N, 9.23; S, 7.09. $C_{27}H_{22}N_2O_2S$ requires: C, 71.52; H, 5.08; N, 9.27; S, 7.06%).

Nitrosation of 2: A solution of 2 (0.596 g, 0.002 mol) was dissolved in 1:1 HCl (2 ml) and then cooled in an ice-bath. Cold 10% $NaNO_2$ solution (6 ml) was then added dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture was stirred for further 30 min at room temperature when the 1-nitroso derivative (7) separated out as a fine white solid. The solid was filtered, washed with water (3 × 20 ml), and recrystallised from ethanol/water (1:1), (0.621 g, 95%), m.p. 188° (Found: C, 77.02; H, 5.18; N, 12.80. $C_{21}H_{17}N_2O$ requires: C, 77.06; H, 5.20; N, 12.84%).

5-Nitroacenaphthene: Acenaphthene was converted to 5-nitroacenaphthene by the reported method⁷ but instead of glacial acetic acid, acetic anhydride was used as the solvent. It was recrystallised from ethanol, (92%), m.p. 106°.

1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenamine: 5-Nitroacenaphthene was converted to 1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenamine by the reported method⁸. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°), (70%), m.p. 108°.

3-[(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-2,4-pentanedione (8): The amine obtained above was diazotised and the diazonium salt solution of the amine (0.05 mol) was coupled with an ice-cold solution of

acetyl acetone (5.1 ml, 0.05 mol) in acetone (60 ml) containing sodium acetate (15 g). The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min and allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 h. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water (2 × 20 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol, (9.8 g, 70%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 72.82; H, 5.69; N, 9.92. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires: C, 72.86; H, 5.71; N, 10%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.4 (6H, s, $COCH_3$), 3.35 (4H, s, CH_2 of acenaphthene), 7.3–8.35 (5H, m, ArH), 11.9–12.1 (1H, br, NH exchangeable with D_2O).

4-[(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (9): To the ketone (8; 0.28 g, 0.001 mol) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml), 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.05 ml, 0.001 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed gently for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water (3 × 20 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol, (0.138 g, 50%), m.p. 90° (Found: C, 73.94; H, 5.79; N, 20.26. $C_{17}H_{16}N_4$ requires: C, 73.91; H, 5.80; N, 20.29%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 320 (NH), 2 910 (CH_2 of acenaphthene), 1 665, 1 580, 1 495 (C=C and C=N of pyrazole) and 1 410 cm^{-1} (N=N, aromatic); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.05 (3H, s, N=CCH₃), 2.6 (3H, s, -C=C(-N)-CH₃), 3.4 (4H, s, CH_2 of acenaphthene), 3.875 (1H, s, NH of pyrazole) and 7.35–8.358 (5H, m, ArH).

1-Acetyl-4-[(1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrazole (10): Method A: The pyrazole (9; 0.276 g, 0.001 mol) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and the solution refluxed for 3 h. It was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid product (10) was filtered, washed with water (2 × 20 ml), and recrystallised from ethanol-water (1:1), (0.175 g, 55%), m.p. 250° (Found: C, 71.65; H, 5.65; N, 17.58. $C_{19}H_{18}N_4O$ requires: C, 71.70; H, 5.66; N, 17.61%); ν_{max} (KBr) 2 920 (CH_2 of acenaphthene), 1 670, 1 585, 1 490 (C=C and C=N of pyrazole), 1 650 (C=O, N-C=O) and 1 415 cm^{-1} (N=N, aromatic).

Method B: A mixture of 8 (0.28 g, 0.001 mol) and an equimolar quantity of 99% hydrazine hydrate was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water (3 × 20 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol-water (1:1), (0.143 g, 45%) m.p. 250°. Analytical and spectroscopic data were identical with the sample synthesised by Method A.

4-[(1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenyl)azo]-3,5-dimethyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (11): To a solution of 8 (0.28 g, 0.001 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), phenyl hydrazine (0.1 ml, 0.001 mol) was added, and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. It was then cooled and poured into crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol as a pale yellow solid (0.158 g, 45%), m.p. 124° (Found: C, 78.46; H, 5.66; N,

15.86. $C_{23}H_{20}N_4$ requires: C, 78.41; H, 5.68; N, 15.91%; ν_{max} (KBr) 2920 (CH_2 of acenaphthene), 1670, 1560, 1490 (C=C and C=N of pyrazole), 1415 (N=N, aromatic), 1370 cm^{-1} ($C_{4,7}-N$); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.075 (3H, s, N=C- CH_3), 2.65 (3H, s, -C=C(-N)- CH_3), 3.4 (4H, s, CH_2 of acenaphthene) and 7.35-8.362 (10H, m, ArH).

Screening for antibacterial activity: All the compounds were screened *in vitro* for biological activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus megaterium* and *Salmonella typhosa* using concentrations of 2 and 5 mg/ml by the ditch-plate technique⁹. The compound 3a was active against all organisms used except *B. megaterium*. 3b, 5c, 6b, 6c and 11 were active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* at the concentration levels employed. 2, 4, 5b, 6d, 9 and 10 were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* at the concentration level of 5 mg/ml. 3c and 6a were active against *E. coli* at the concentration level of 5 mg/ml. 4, 5c, 6c and 11 were active against *B. megaterium* at the concentration level of 5 mg/ml. 6c and 11 were found to

be active against *S. typhosa* at the concentration level of 5 mg/ml. The compounds 5a and 7 were inactive against all the organisms.

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